

***X. oryzae* and its pathotypes in Indonesia**

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Leaf blight may damage rice in Indonesia when susceptible varieties are planted and weather conditions are suitable. Studies by various researchers in the past 5 years conclude that several pathotypes occur.

Based on the Kozaka Grouping System, four pathotypes have been identified and labeled pathotypes III, IV, V, and VI. Pathotype III appears to be the most common and most widespread in Indonesia. Pathotypes I and II do not currently occur there. Pathotype IV has a broad spectrum of virulence and can infect varieties of all groups.

To differentiate pathotypes in Indonesia, the four groups of varieties in the Kozaka System are expanded into five: Kinmaze, Kogyoku, Rantai Emas, Wase Aikoku, and Jawa. The Indonesian differentials are Kencana and Padi Jambu, representing the Kinmaze group; IR5, representing Kogyoku; Rantai Emas and Tetep, representing Rantai Emas; Kuntulan, representing Wase Aikoku; and Remaja and Jelita, representing Jawa.

Tests using the bacterial exudation technique indicate that several varieties have moderate to high levels of quantitative resistance to *X. oryzae* in Indonesia. They are Dara, Remaja, Jelita, IR20, IR22, IR26, IR28, IR29, IR30, Syntha, Dewi Ratih, Pelita I/1, Pelita I/2, and Nihonbare. ❧

***Xanthomonas oryzae* strains in Thailand**

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Samples of bacterial leaf blight of rice were collected from four parts of Thailand from 1972 to 1977: 31 isolates from the central region; 28 isolates, northern; 13, northeastern; and 26, southern. Their pathogenic behavior was tested on three rice varieties that show different degrees of resistance or

susceptibility in Thailand. The varieties were PN 16/Sigadis and IR8/Tadukan (resistant), and RD 1 (highly susceptible). Plants with four fully developed leaves were inoculated beside the main vein at the middle part of each leaf blade by single-needle pinprick. Observations were made 15 days after inoculation, using the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) scale. Comparisons of the pathogenicity of the isolates were also made from bacteriophage tests using the streak plate method. The pathogenic strains of bacterial leaf blight of rice in Thailand seem to fall into three groups. Pathogenic strain A produced big lesions in both resistant and susceptible varieties. Strain B produced big lesions only in the susceptible variety and small lesions in the resistant varieties. Strain C produced small lesions in both susceptible and resistant varieties. The predominant pathogenic strain was strain B. According to their sensitivity to the five types of bacteriophages, the isolates of *X. oryzae* in Thailand fell into 12 groups (A, B, C, ... L). Bacterium strain A predominated; it was distributed throughout the country. Strain B was mainly in central and southern areas, and Strain C was found everywhere in Thailand except in the northeast. Strain E was predominant in southern Thailand. Strains A, B, C, D, and E encompassed more isolates than the others, which presented only one or two isolates each. The fact that strain B was sensitive to all of the Thai *X. oryzae* bacteriophages was useful for the forecasting of bacterial leaf blight of rice in Thailand. No correlation was observed between pathogenic strains and phage-sensitive strains. ❧

Grouping of *Xanthomonas oryzae* isolates in terms of virulence in Japan

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Grouping of *Xanthomonas oryzae* isolates in terms of pathogenicity or virulence has been attempted in Japan since 1957. Isolates from various Japanese sites were assigned to group A or B, each containing three subgroups, or to group I, II, or III, by needle prick inoculation of young leaves or flag leaves

of the differential rice varieties. Some workers used more than 10 rice varieties for differentiation; others used wild rices and weeds as well. Classification methods and criteria varied markedly. Multineedle prick inoculation of the flag leaves of four groups of differential varieties (Kinmaze, Kogyoku, Rantai Emas, and Wase Aikoku) has recently been recommended to standardize reporting of pathogenicity in Japan. Isolates can be grouped as follows:

- Group I virulent to only Kinmaze varieties
- Group II virulent to Kinmaze and Kogyoku varieties
- Group III virulent to Kinmaze, Kogyoku, and Rantai Emas varieties
- Group IV virulent to all varieties

The criterion was established by inoculating the leaves of young seedlings with Japanese isolates only. Some attempts were made to apply the criterion to tropical isolates. Because using tropical isolates in the field in Japan is impracticable, young seedlings were inoculated in the greenhouse. Pathogens with higher virulence than the Japanese isolates seem to be frequent and widely distributed in the tropical areas, particularly in India, Cambodia, and Thailand. With some exceptions, virulent isolates showed high virulence to all varieties, isolates with low virulence expressed it with all varieties. Clearcut specialization in pathogenicity was not observed. By the above criterion, most of the highly virulent isolates were considered to belong to Group III or IV.

An isolate showing a distinct pathotype was reported recently to exist in Bali, Indonesia. A group V (virulent to Kinmaze and Wase-Aikoku group varieties) was proposed. Pathotype differentiation was also noticed at the International Rice Research Institute. When young seedlings are inoculated, the virulence of *X. oryzae* isolates seems generally to vary quantitatively, depending on the combinations of isolates and hosts, without clearcut specialization. The groups suggested above will, therefore, be separated into the smaller clusters according to judgments of virulence, or by additions to the differential varieties. Of course, data suggesting pathogenic specialization

were often obtained, but were too much complicated to be analyzed. More intensive studies are needed in each country, using adult plants and sophisticated techniques. ❧

Pathogenic strains of *Xanthomonas oryzae* and related resistant and susceptible rice varieties in Korea

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Two phage-type strains of *Xanthomonas oryzae* were identified in Korea by the use of four different bacteriophages, in 1968, and seven had been identified by 1971. The seven strains were categorized according to virulence into three groups, but the groups were not called pathotypes or races.

By 1976, five groups of pathotypes were recognized in Korea. To classify the isolates, they were inoculated to four groups of differential varieties. Of 67 isolates collected from limited areas of the country, 22 belonged to pathotype I, 8 to pathotype II, 2 to III, 5 to IV, and 30 to V.

Pathotype I attacks only Kinmaze-group varieties including IRI 323, 326, 327, 330, Milyang 21, 23, 28, 34, Suweon 264, 265, 267, 268, 271, Jinheung, and Glutinous Tong-il. Pathotype II attacks, in addition to those varieties, Kokyoku-group varieties such as Iri 319, 328, Milyang 25, and Suweon 263. Pathotype III attacks all varietal groups except the Wase-Aikoku group varieties (Milyang 30), and pathotype IV attacks all the varieties tested. Pathotype V attacks varieties of the Kinmaze and Wase-Aikoku groups.

During the 1976 growing season, severe epidemics of kresiek disease occurred in areas where the new variety Milyang 23 had been introduced. It was the first time that kresiek was officially reported in Korea. Of all cultivars used in studies of kresiek, Milyang 23 showed the most susceptible reactions to all five pathotypes. The relationship between pathotypes and kresiek symptoms was not clearly proved, although it seemed to be affected by inoculum concentrations, inoculation sites, and varietal differences. ❧

Pathogenic strains of *Xanthomonas oryzae* in the Philippines

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The virulence patterns of *X. oryzae* isolates collected in the Philippines from 1963 to 1976 were evaluated on four host varieties: IR8, which has shown no genes for resistance to bacterial blight; IR20, which has the dominant gene *Xa 4*; IR1545-339, which carries the recessive gene *xa 5*; and DV85, which has one recessive gene similar to *xa 5* and a dominant gene that is different from *Xa 4*.

Pathogenic strains or races clearly exist in the population of *X. oryzae* in the Philippines. Most of the 83 isolates belong to one group that we call the common strain, exemplified by isolate PXO 61. Host genotypes carrying either of the two major genes (*Xa 4* or *xa 5*) are resistant to that strain. The Isabela strain is exemplified by the isolate PXO 79 collected in Davao; the host genotype carrying the recessive gene *xa 5*

is resistant. The third group of isolates, which makes up a small portion of the present collection and is typified by PXO 71 from the Palawan area, overcomes the resistance of host genotypes that carry both the dominant and recessive genes. It appears that PXO 71 is more compatible with genotypes with *xa 5* than with those with *Xa 4*. It always produces more lesions on IR1545-339 than on IR20. DV85 is resistant to all isolates. A variety like IR8, with no apparent genes for resistance to bacterial blight, is susceptible to the three groups of isolates. All isolates under study produced lesions on IR8, but isolates such as PXO 10 that have weak virulence produced considerably fewer lesions.

The results also confirmed that isolates compatible with a certain host genotype are present in an area before the particular host genotype is widely planted. PXO 71 is one of the isolates found in Palawan in 1974; some isolates of the Isabela strain were collected in Davao in 1963. ❧

Pest management and control

INSECTS

Eriophyid mite appears on rice in Thailand

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The 4-legged eriophyid mites are quite uncommon on rice. In Keifer's 1967 index, only one rice-infesting species is given — *Eriophyes bakkeri* Keifer, which was described from Africa. Another species — *Cheiracus sulcatus* Keifer — has been found in Thailand. I encountered it on the undersides of mature blades in paddy at Ban Pa Ha, Chiang Rai Province, North Thailand.

The infestation was heavy, but it occurred on old leaves blemished by other agents. It would therefore be premature, on the basis of visual inspection only, to attribute damage to the mite. The mite has to be evaluated under controlled conditions. ❧

Grasshoppers on rice in Pakistan

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Rice suffers considerable loss due to grasshopper attack in Pakistan. The important species are *Heroglyphus banian* (F.) and *Oxya multidentata* Will. *H. banian*, earlier reported as a Serious pest in the plains, currently occurs mostly in hilly areas. Intensive cultivation in the Plains may be responsible for the destruction of egg pods there. Abundance of *H. banian* in the hills may be due to favorable climate or undisturbed oviposition sites. *O. multidentata* is found all over Pakistan but is more abundant in hilly areas. *Oxya velox* (F.), a serious pest in almost all rice-growing countries, is of minor significance here. It is found only in the hills and foothills. *Acrida exaltata* Wlk.,